

Integrated pest management – insects

Rice pest abundance in Bihar and Orissa States, India

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Developing improved methods of rice pest management is a component of the Indo-British Fertilizer Education Project in six states of N.E. India. Variability of the rice pest complex in different areas is associated with differences in cropping intensity, irrigation, variety, fertilizer, and pesticide use.

Rice fauna differences can be shown by comparing 1988 dry season crops in Sindri, Dhanbad District (eastern Bihar) and in Arisol, Puri District (coastal Orissa). In Dhanbad, except in isolated patches, only a wet season crop is grown; in Puri, a rainfed crop is grown in the wet season (Jul-Dec) and an irrigated crop in the dry season (Jan-May).

We sampled at both locations approximately 50, 70, and 90 dafter transplanting, using a D-vac suction sampler. Rice pest species found are shown in Figure 1. Populations of green leafhopper (GLH) were significantly higher at Sindri on both the second and third sampling dates. In the third sample, populations of brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and zigzag leafhopper were significantly higher at Arisol. BPH and WBPH populations tended to increase across the season, particularly at Arisol.

In general, patterns of relative pest abundance were similar most years; 1987 average densities at 50 and 70 d after transplanting are shown for comparison.

With the exception of GLH, the very low abundance of pests on the dry season (Bihar) rice crop in Sindri suggests there may be low local carryover of pests from

one wet Season to the next. The GLH population may have been initiated by immigrants from double-cropping areas in neighboring West Bengal, where GLH is common in light trap catches.

Differences in rice varieties planted at the two sites are unlikely to be responsible for hopper density differences: IR36 grown in Sindri is rated as moderately resistant to BPH and resistant to GLH;

CR190 grown in Arisol is rated as resistant to both pests.

The most abundant natural enemies of rice pests at both sites were *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and Lycosidae and Tetragnathidae spiders. There were significantly more natural enemies in Arisol than in Sindri on the third sampling date. Ratios of natural enemies to pests were much higher at Arisol, where natural enemies showed some tendency to increase in association with increasing pest density (Fig. 2). ■

1. Mean densities (n = 50) of the 8 most abundant pest species on dry season rice CR190 in Arisol and IR36 in Sindri. 1 = *Nilaparvata lugens* (brown planthopper), 2 = *Sogatella furcifera* (whitebacked planthopper), 3 = *Nephotettix* spp. (green leafhopper), 4 = *Recilia dorsalis* (zigzag leafhopper), 5 = *Cofana spectra* (white jassid), 6 = stem borers, 7 = *Leptocorisa* spp. (rice bug), 8 = *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* (rice leafhopper).